

FORMATION OF SIGN FUNCTIONS AND CHARACTERISTICS OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS

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Abstract. This paper considers Formation of sign functions and characteristics of phraseological units and borrowed phraseological units that not only figuratively describe what is happening, but also simultaneously translate symbols, stereotypes, standards, mythologemes, assuming the function of a sign of culture.

Keywords: Phraseology, Linguistics, phraseological units, language.

Phraseology (from the Greek phrasis and logos), a linguistic discipline that studies stable idiomatic (in the broad sense) phrases - phraseological units; the set of phraseological units themselves of a particular language is also called its phraseology. A lot has been written about the subject of phraseology, its problems and aspects. Phraseology as an independent linguistic discipline has existed for only more than half a century, and there are still many unresolved problems and unexplored issues.

The central issue of phraseology is the definition of phraseologism. At present, there is a relative unity of views on the phraseological unit. In the overwhelming majority of definitions, a number of features of phraseological units are distinguished, which distinguish it from both a word and a free phrase. Being an independent linguistic unit, a phraseological phrase is characterized by special semantic, structural and functional features. The semantic one is singled out as the main feature, since it is the semantic transformation that makes it possible to limit the phraseological unit from both free and stable non-phraseological units, to ensure its stability, integrity and reproducibility. Phraseologisms are an integral and specially distinguished component of the language, the most striking, original, unusual, "individual", culturally significant and nationally specific, capable of expressing in a concentrated way not only the features of a given language, but also its speakers, their attitude, mindset, mentality, national character and style of thinking.

"Phraseology as a linguistic discipline is still in the stage of" latent development "... but it has not yet taken shape as a mature fruit of preparatory work And we already need to single out such a discipline, because the amateurish helplessness, inconsistency and failure of passing, random analysis of this material in lexicography, style, syntax". (Larin, 1956, pp. 200-201).

The phraseology of any language, and especially English, has always been of scientific interest and attracted the attention of researchers. Phraseological units are a special phenomenon in the language. They are figurative means of language, means of decorating and enriching speech. Phraseologisms fill in the gaps in the language system, which cannot fully provide the name of the new aspects of reality known to man. The use of phraseological units weakens the contradictions between the needs of thinking and the limited lexical resources of the language. Most of the phraseological combinations that have arisen in the sphere of live colloquial speech have certain emotional, expressive meanings. Phraseological units are a powerful expressive means of language. They serve for figurative interpretation of phenomena.

Phraseological units are the creation of a people, a manifestation of their wisdom and linguistic instinct. A lot can be said about phraseological units. The theory of phraseological units was founded at the beginning of the twentieth century. In Russia, this theory began to be developed and a number of interesting works were written by Viktor Vladimirovich Vinogradov.

Phraseologisms are considered highly informative units of the language; they cannot be regarded as "decorations" or "excesses". A similar formulation of phraseological units is found in some works and is currently outdated. Phraseological units are one of the linguistic universals, since there are no languages without phraseological units. English phraseology is very rich.

The founder of the theory of phraseology is the Swiss linguist of French origin Charles Bally (1865-1947). Bally first systematized word combinations in his books "Essay on Stylistics" and "French Stylistics" (BallyCh., 1905, 1909). Bally included a chapter on phraseology in his books on style. In the first book, he singled out four groups of phrases: 1) free phrases (*les groupe ments libres*), i.e. combinations lacking stability, decomposing after their formation; 2) habitual combinations (*les groupe mentu suels*), i.e. phrases with a relatively free connection of components that allow some changes, for example, *une grave maladie* - a serious disease (*une dangereuse, serieuse maladie* - a dangerous, serious disease); 3) phraseological series (*les series phraseologiques*), i.e. groups of words in which two adjacent concepts merge almost into one.

The number of phraseological units borrowed from the French language is quite large. They came to English by tracing the original expressions.

French culture, like any other, has its own system of values. The list of dominant values varies in different studies. However, among some common features of the French cultural world, the French themselves name the ability to perceive a foreign culture, dynamism, mobility, tendency to update, as well as orderliness and clarity. Several concepts-constants have a bright reflection in phraseological units.

In English, phraseological units of French origin manifest themselves as active expressions that reflect such concepts as: honor, honesty, justice, sense of duty. This is confirmed by such expressions: "A point of honor" - a matter of honor (*Point d'honneur*); "Affair of honor" - "a matter of honor", a duel (*Affair d'honneur*), where the dominant characteristic is honor (*honneur*). "Espouse smb's quarrel" - stand up for someone, help someone get justice (*Epouser la quarelle de qn*); "Make a point of smth." - to consider something important, essential, to consider something as one's duty, to set oneself as a rule (*Faire un point de*); "Empty the bag" - to speak out, put everything clean (*Vider le sac*).

In phraseological units of French origin, there are also such important linguoculturological characteristics that appear in many expressions: beauty, women, joy of life. Such expressions characterizing the fair sex, i.e. women, for example: "The fair (the gentle) sex" - the fair sex, women (*le beau sexe*); "there's a woman in it" - a woman is involved here, look for a woman (*cherchez la femme*); "the eyes are the mirror of the soul" - the eyes are the mirror of the soul (*les yeux sont le miroirde l'ame*); "make good cheer" - feast, have fun, treat yourself (*faire bonne chere*).

Laziness and idleness are reflected in the national concept sphere of the French as one of the main vices: "Burn candle at both ends" - burn life, waste strength, health (*Buriers la chandelle par les deux bouts*); "Idleness makes the wit rust" – last. the mind is dull from idleness (*L'oisivete rouille l'espirit*); Idleness is

the mother (the root) of all evil (sin or vice) - last. idleness is the mother of all vices (L'oisivete est la mere de tous les vices); "The land of Cockaigne (Cockayne)" - a fabulous country of abundance and idleness, an earthly paradise (Pays de cocagne).

In the phraseological fund of the English language, one can also find phraseological units borrowed from the Arabic language. For example, from the tales of "A Thousand and One Nights" several expressions came into English: Aladdin's lamp (book) - Aladdin's magic lamp (a talisman that fulfills all the wishes of its owner). The PU to rub the lamp is connected with the same tale - it is easy to fulfill your desire; Alnaschar's dream (book) - empty dreams, fantasizing (in one of the tales of "A Thousand and One Nights" it is said about Alnashar, who bought glassware with all his money and put them in a basket, but, dreaming about how he would become rich man, and angry with his future wife, he hit the basket and broke all the glass); the old man of the sea - a person who is difficult to get rid of, get rid of, an obsessive person (a hint of an episode in one of the tales, which tells how Sinbad the Sailor could not get rid of the old man who sat on his shoulders); an open Sesame - "Sesame, open!", a quick and easy way to achieve something (the magic words that opened the door to the cave of the robbers in the fairy tale "Ali Baba and the Forty Thieves")

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